

THE FORMATION OF INDIVIDUAL IDENTITY IN BILDUNGSROMAN FICTION

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Abstract. The article discusses bildungsroman novels shows the gradual transformation of the protagonist's psyche in a way that appears natural to the reader. The protagonist's spirituality and mentality may evolve slowly and progressively throughout the work. By passing through different stages, the protagonist achieves spiritual maturity and develops into a fully mature individual in society.

Keywords: formation, bildungsroman, psychological state, poetic device.

To enhance the artistic quality of literary works belonging to the Bildungsroman genre, the writer pays attention to the continuous and gradual development of the protagonist's inner world. For example, by describing the external appearance of a character, the writer seeks to reveal that character's psychological state.

In bildungsroman works, the characters' thoughts, actions, and relationships with the people around them may change over time. The writer attempts to present the gradual transformation of the protagonist's psyche in a way that appears natural to the reader. The protagonist's spirituality and mentality may evolve slowly and progressively throughout the work.

"By passing through the following four stages, the protagonist achieves spiritual maturity and develops into a fully mature individual within society."¹

METHODS.

The research is based on linguopoetic analysis which is necessary for analyzing bildungsroman works.

1. The writer creates circumstances in which the protagonist experiences the pain of separation in order to mature into a perfect human being. For example, "In Uzbek classical literature, the works of Navoi play an important role in the spiritual development of the younger generation. His works address such issues as respecting parents, teachers, and elders; acquiring knowledge and enlightenment; possessing good morals; and staying away from evil. Undoubtedly, these ideas are closely connected with the ideal of the perfect human being, which has remained a universal aspiration throughout all ages."²

Consequently, in Jack London's novel "Martin Eden" Martin Eden the fact that the protagonist grows up without parents exemplifies a characteristic feature of Bildungsroman novels.

2. The writer places various obstacles in the protagonist's path in the novel or creates conditions for the character to experience strong emotional feelings.³ For example, Martin Eden faces many hardships, experiencing life's challenges with his innocent and fragile heart.

3. Travel or adventures are also an important poetic device that allows the main character to learn many things, gain experience, and be prepared for any terrible events.⁴

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS.

¹ <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/what-is-a-bildungsroman-definition-and-examples-of-bildungsroman-in-literature#the-history-of-the-bildungsroman>

² <http://fitrat.uz/alisher-navoj-da-osi-va-barkamollik/>

³ <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/what-is-a-bildungsroman-definition-and-examples-of-bildungsroman-in-literature#the-history-of-the-bildungsroman>

⁴ The same source.

In Jack London's novel *Martin Eden*, the protagonist's extensive sea voyages and pursuit of knowledge help lay the foundation for his development into a mature individual in society.

4. Conflict and disagreements are sometimes a literary device that leads characters to make mistakes, which in turn become turning points in their lives. *Martin Eden*'s disagreement with a journalist has a significant impact on his life.

The moral development of literary characters and their growth into mature individuals defines an important artistic aspect of a writer's work. In this sense, the novel *Martin Eden* belongs to the Bildungsroman genre, and its plot is also narrated from the perspective of the main character. This narrative feature is also characteristic of Bildungsroman works.

Jack London's *Martin Eden* is also considered a semi-autobiographical Künstlerroman. The term "Künstlerroman" comes from German and means "the artist's novel." It is regarded as a subtype of the Bildungsroman, in which, toward the end of the work, the main character rejects the events of ordinary life. In particular, in Jack London's *Martin Eden*, the protagonist, *Martin Eden*, based on Nietzschean theory, does not change his attitude toward life. Through the character of *Martin Eden*, Jack London suggests that Nietzsche's ideas may potentially destroy a person.

In addition to Jack London's *Martin Eden*, we also studied other works belonging to the Bildungsroman genre.

Furthermore, it is necessary to mention James Joyce, one of the famous 20th-century modernist writers who contributed to the development of Irish literature through Bildungsroman-type works. In his novel *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*, the protagonist's childhood and coming-of-age process are portrayed through his intense emotional and psychological experience of understanding the world, as well as his search for his life path and the growth of his spirituality.⁵

1. The intellectual development of the protagonist is also shown. In the novel, Stephen Dedalus becomes aware of existing injustices, perceives them emotionally and intellectually, and is depicted as struggling for his own rights.

"It was unfair and cruel because the doctor had told him not to read without glasses and he had written home to his father that morning to send him a new pair. And Father Arnall had said that he need not study till the new glasses came. Then to be called a schemer before the class and to be pandied when he always got the card for first or second and was the leader of the Yorkists! How could the prefect of studies know that it was a trick?"⁶

Stephen Dedalus's struggle against injustice became a driving force in his development as an individual in society. During his adolescence, Stephen was punished by a school inspector who did not trust him because his glasses were broken and he could not study properly. Unable to tolerate this injustice, the boy complained to the headmaster of the school, which showed that his intelligence was beginning to develop and that he had started to stand up for his rights.

2. The protagonist's moral and ethical development:

Stephen Dedalus's moral and ethical growth corresponds to his transition from childhood to adolescence. His interest in literature increases, and he begins writing poems. Later, he falls in love with a girl named Emma and writes letters to her.

"The verses passed from his mind to his lips and, murmuring them over, he felt the rhythmic movement of a villanelle pass through them. The rose-like glow sent forth its rays of rhyme; ways, days, blaze, praise, raise. Its rays burned up the world, consumed the hearts of men and angels: the rays from the rose that was her wilful heart.

Your eyes have set man's heart ablaze

⁵ Sheys G. *Psychological Realism of Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*. March 26, 2010.

⁶ J. Joyce. *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*. Free eBooks at Planet eBook.com. – P.61.

And you have had your will of him.

Are you not weary of ardent ways?"⁷

3. Stephen Dedalus's inner experiences and the development of his psychological world are reflected in his internal monologue. In particular, the protagonist's awareness and feeling of his own sins and his visit to a priest contributed to his spiritual growth. In order to free himself from inner suffering, he becomes ready to endure all kinds of hardships.

"He knelt to say his penance, praying in a corner of the dark nave; and his prayers ascended to heaven from his purified heart like perfume streaming upwards from a heart of white rose. The muddy streets were gay. He strode homeward, conscious of an invisible grace pervading and making light his limbs. In spite of all he had done it. He had confessed and God had pardoned him. His soul was made fair and holy once more, holy and happy."⁸

CONCLUSION.

Stephen Dedalus succeeds in restraining his desires. He strives to purify his conscience, which is filled with despair within his inner world. His way of thinking, once simple, gradually becomes more complex. He distances himself from the social environment and finds his place in society as an independent individual.

Stephen Dedalus reads the works of Aristotle and Thomas Aquinas with great interest and avoids spending time walking with his peers. The world around him seems to fade from his sight, and he feels as if he can no longer express himself in words. The writer resolves the protagonist's fate by having him leave Ireland and go to Paris. The Bildungsroman genre occupies an important place in world literature by portraying the spiritual, psychological, moral, and intellectual development of the protagonist. Writers of Bildungsroman novels strive to reveal the gradual formation of an individual through life experiences, emotional struggles, conflicts, separation, and self-discovery.

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⁷ J. Joyce. A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man. Free eBooks at Planet eBook.com. – P.271.

⁸ J. Joyce. A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man. Free eBooks at Planet eBook.com. – P.179.

